

Intellectual
Property
Office

Application

GB2614145.7

Application details

Application number	GB2614145.7
Application title	M.A.R.S. Companion: System and Method for Autonomous Physical Embodiment, Hardware-Anchored Identity, and Trust-Gated Introspective Agency in Artificial Intelligence
Status	Filed

Dates

Lodged date	18 June 2026
Filing date	18 June 2026

Applicants

Name	Address
Aleksandr Sarkisian	